

LONG-TERM IMPACT OF : RIVER RESTORATION

WITH IMOGEN EDWARDS

Rivers are vital, but human activities have disrupted their natural flow, harming ecosystems and worsening floods. Restoration seeks to reverse these impacts to help rivers recover.

Immy's PhD studies how restored rivers evolve over time. She studies the Cole and Lymington Rivers in the UK, using long-term ecological and hydrological data to assess the effectiveness of restoration so we can understand how to better protect rivers in a changing environment.

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COLE RIVER
WEST OF OXFORD, IN THE
THAMES RIVER BASIN DISTRICT.

LYMINGTON RIVER
NEAR SOUTHAMPTON, IN THE NEW FOREST
NATIONAL PARK, A PROTECTED AREA IN THE
SOUTH-EAST RIVER BASIN DISTRICT.

RIVERS ARE VITAL, BUT HUMAN ACTIVITIES HAVE DISRUPTED THEIR NATURAL FLOW, HARMING ECOSYSTEMS AND WORSENING FLOODS. THESE RIVERS HAVE BEEN HEAVILY MODIFIED OVER CENTURIES.

THE LYMINGTON RIVER WAS AFFECTED BY FORESTRY AND STRAIGHTENING OF STREAMS IN THE 19TH CENTURY, DRYING OUT THE LANDSCAPE, DISRUPTING SEASONAL FLOODING AND DEGRADING WOODLANDS.

THE COLE RIVER WAS SHAPED BY HUMAN ACTIVITY FOR NEARLY 900 YEARS, MAINLY FOR MILLING AND AGRICULTURE.

BOTH RIVERS WERE RESTORED STARTING IN THE 1990S.

WHILE EACH RESTORATION WAS TAILORED TO THEIR LOCATION, THEY SHARED COMMON GOALS :

IMPROVING FLOOD STORAGE, ENHANCING HABITAT DIVERSITY, AND CREATING A MORE AESTHETICALLY PLEASING RIVER ENVIRONMENT."

MY RESEARCH LOOKS AT HOW WELL THESE EFFORTS WORKED. BUT HOW DO I STUDY THAT? THROUGH ECOLOGY AND HYDROLOGY!

FOR THE LYMINGTON RIVER, I FOCUS ON HYDROLOGY AND HYDRAULICS. WHAT'S THE DIFFERENCE?

HYDROLOGY IS ABOUT THE NATURAL WATER CYCLE, HOW WATER MOVES FROM ONE 'COMPARTMENT' TO ANOTHER ON EARTH: THE OCEANS, THE SURFACE OR UNDERGROUND ON THE CONTINENTS. IT COVERS RAINFALL, RUNOFF, INFILTRATION INTO THE SOIL, EVAPORATION, AND SO ON.

HYDRAULICS IS ALL ABOUT THE PHYSICS OF MOVING WATER, HOW WATER FLOW IN SPECIFIC PLACES, WHETHER NATURAL OR ARTIFICIAL: IN STREAMS, LAKES, IRRIGATION CHANNELS, LAND, URBAN PAVEMENT, SOILS OR AQUIFERS. IT LOOKS AT THINGS LIKE WATER LEVELS AND FLOW SPEED, WHICH ARE CLOSELY LINKED TO FLUID MECHANICS.

ONE THING I STUDY IS RIVER ROUGHNESS - HOW MUCH RESISTANCE THE RIVERBED, BANKS, VEGETATION OR ARTIFICIAL OBSTACLES OPPOSE TO FLOWING WATER.

FOR EXAMPLE, A SMOOTH, STRAIGHT, OBSTACLE-FREE RIVER FLOWS FAST.

IF THERE ARE SMALL STONES IN THE RIVERBED, THEY WILL EXERT A COUNTERFORCE, AND THE RIVER WILL THEN BE SLOWER

AND IF THE RIVERBED IS FULL OF ROCKS, PLANTS AND FALLEN BRANCHES, THEN THE WATER ENCOUNTERS A LOT OF RESISTANCE, ITS SPEED IS 'BROKEN' BY ALL THESE OBSTACLES.

FOR THIS SITE, WE HAVE OVER 40 YEARS OF HYDROLOGICAL AND HYDRAULIC DATA, WHICH IS RARE. THIS WILL CERTAINLY ALLOW US TO ANSWER THE QUESTION: HAS RESTORATION CHANGED THE RIVER'S NATURAL HYDROLOGY?

TIME PLAYS A CRUCIAL ROLE HERE, ALTHOUGH WE AS HUMANS ARE CAUGHT UP IN OUR DAILY ROUTINES, WE DON'T OFTEN NOTICE THE SLOW NATURAL PROCESSES. WHILE WOODY DEBRIS AND ROCKS MAY SLOW WATER FOR NOW, OVER DECADES OR CENTURIES, THE CONSTANT FLOW OF WATER WILL WEAR THEM DOWN, ALLOWING THE RIVER TO FLOW FASTER.

FOR THE COLE RIVER, I FOCUS ON ECOLOGY AND BIOLOGY. ECOLOGY IS A BRANCH OF BIOLOGY. BIOLOGY IS A VERY VERY BROAD FIELD.

FOR EXAMPLE, WOODLICE ARE DECOMPOSERS THAT ARE VERY SENSITIVE TO DEHYDRATION, SO IF YOU FIND THEM IN SOIL, IT IS VERY LIKELY THAT THIS SOIL IS MOIST, COOL AND RICH IN ORGANIC MATTER.

MY RESEARCH USES BIO-INDICATORS, ORGANISMS - PLANT OR ANIMAL - THAT TELL US ABOUT ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS.

I STUDY MACROINVERTEBRATES - INVERTEBRATES LARGE ENOUGH TO SEE WITHOUT A MICROSCOPE (THINK INSECTS AND TINY AQUATIC CREATURES).

WHY THEM? BECAUSE THEY'RE ABUNDANT IN ALL TYPES OF RUNNING WATER, EASY TO SAMPLE, AND PROVIDE GREAT INSIGHTS INTO ECOSYSTEM HEALTH.

MY WORK INVOLVES: FIELDWORK - COLLECTING SAMPLES (A FUN PART OF MY JOB, WITH LOTS OF FRESH AIR!)

LAB ANALYSIS - EXAMINING SAMPLES TO DETERMINE SPECIES RICHNESS AND THEIR RELATIVE ABUNDANCE.

WHAT IS IT, YOU MAY ASK? LET'S TAKE AN EXAMPLE WITH THE MAYFLIES!

IN THIS SAMPLE, I FOUND 5 DIFFERENT SPECIES. THAT'S THE SPECIES RICHNESS.

ALTOGETHER, THERE ARE 20 INDIVIDUALS - AND 10 OF THEM ARE MAYFLIES. SO MAYFLIES MAKE UP 50% OF THE SAMPLE. THAT'S THEIR RELATIVE ABUNDANCE.

BY ANALYZING THESE BIO-INDICATORS, I CAN ASSESS THE HEALTH OF THE COLE RIVER'S ECOSYSTEM AND THE IMPACT OF RESTORATION EFFORTS.

RESTORATION SUCCESS ISN'T JUST ABOUT ECOLOGY OR HYDROLOGY - IT'S ABOUT BOTH. WE NEED BOTH PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA TO EVALUATE A RIVER'S HEALTH.

NATURE ALWAYS SURPRISES US! FOR EXAMPLE, I FOUND MORE MACROINVERTEBRATES IN UNRESTORED SECTIONS OF THE COLE THAN IN RESTORED ONES.

WHY? THE RESTORED AREAS ARE DENSE WITH VEGETATION AND QUITE DARK, WHILE THE UNRESTORED SECTIONS HAVE GRAZED BANKS, WHICH CREATES A MIX OF LIGHT AND SHADE - AND THIS IS EXACTLY WHAT MACROINVERTEBRATES LOVE!

OF COURSE, IT'S NOT JUST ABOUT COUNTING SPECIES, BUT UNDERSTANDING WHAT THEY TELL US AND KNOWING WHICH ONES INDICATE GOOD ECOLOGICAL HEALTH FOR THESE KINDS OF STREAMS.

AND HERE'S THE TRICKY PART: HOW DO WE MEASURE SUCCESS OF RESTORATION?

SHOULD WE COMPARE A RESTORED RIVER TO ITS PRE-RESTORATION STATE? TO A HEALTHY RIVER IN SIMILAR CONDITIONS (REFERENCE ECOSYSTEM)? OR TO HOW IT MIGHT CHANGE IN THE FUTURE UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE? THE ANSWER IS NOT SIMPLE.

RIVER RESTORATION DOESN'T ALWAYS GO EXACTLY AS PLANNED. WE TRY TO REDUCE FLOODING, IMPROVE WATER QUALITY, AND RESTORE HABITATS, BUT NATURE HAS ITS OWN WAY OF RESPONDING, SOMETIMES IN UNEXPECTED WAYS. THAT'S A HUMBLING LESSON!

THAT DOESN'T MEAN WE SHOULD GIVE UP ON RIVER RESTORATION. WE JUST NEED TO STUDY RIVERS OVER A LONG PERIOD OF TIME TO UNDERSTAND THESE COMPLEXITIES BETTER.

THAT'S WHAT MAKES MY RESEARCH EXCITING! IT HIGHLIGHTS THE NEED FOR LONG-TERM MONITORING AND WELL-DOCUMENTED METHODS SO THAT FUTURE SCIENTISTS CAN BUILD ON PAST WORK.

